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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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MUNDARIJA

The Use of Innovative Pedagogical Technologies in the Development of Critical Thinking	16
<i>Gulnar Atakhanova Orinbaevna</i>	
Current Aspects of Designing and Implementing Extracurricular Educational Activities at the Primary General Education Level.....	20
<i>Amankosova Dinara Gabitovna</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tizimida tarbiyachi shaxsiyati va kasbiy mahorati shakllanishining nazariy asoslari....	24
<i>Axmadaliyeva Moxlaroy To'xtapolatovna</i>	
Pedagogical Model and Stages of Teaching Subjects Through a Project-Based Approach	28
<i>Bannayev Qosimjon</i>	
Lotin tili va zamonaviy tibbiy terminologiya: tarixi, vazifasi va amaliy ahamiyati	31
<i>Eshmurodova Shirin Oybekovna</i>	
Motor alaliyaning nonutqiy simptomatikasi	34
<i>Isayeva Mushtariy Alisher qizi</i>	
Talabalar etnomadaniy kompetentligini rivojlantirishning pedagogik-psixologik omillari	38
<i>Isomiddinov Asliddin Baxriddin o'g'li</i>	
Texnologiya darslarida o'quvchilarning texnik savodxonligini robototexnika elementlari asosida rivojlantirish.....	41
<i>Jabborova Umida</i>	
Fizika fanini mutaxassislik fanlari integratsiyasi asosida o'qitishda bo'lajak muhandislarning kasbiy kompetentligini rivojlantirishning ilmiy-nazariy asoslari	45
<i>Xayrullayev Asliddin Isatullayevich</i>	
Talaba tomonidan mutaxassislik tilini o'zlashtirishda monologik nutqni o'rgatishning samarali usullari masalasi haqida.....	51
<i>Karimov N. M.</i>	
Zamonaviy pedagog kadrlar tayyorlashda kasbiy motiv va motivatsiyaning o'rni	54
<i>Melikova Elnora Shuxratovna</i>	
Bo'lajak ingliz tili o'qituvchilarini tayyorlashda pragmatik kompetensiyaning roli.....	58
<i>Mustafayeva Nilufar Ulashovna</i>	
O'quvchilarda iqtisodiy tafakkurni rivojlantirishning pedagogik strategiyalari	62
<i>Nishonova Dilafuz</i>	
Computer-Based Formative Assessment: Advantages and Challenges in Teaching English to High School Students	66
<i>Obidjonova Shokhista Bakhtiyorovna</i>	
Metata'lim texnologiyalari asosida bo'lajak maktabgacha ta'lim mutaxassislarini tayyorlash tizimini takomillashtirish.....	70
<i>O'rolboyeva Durdona Sayfiddin qizi</i>	
Sun'iy intellekt asosidagi darslarning an'anaviy darslarga nisbatan samaradorligini qiyosiy tahlil qilish.....	73
<i>Rasulev Bobirjan Atxamovich</i>	
Pedagogik faoliyatda pedagogning kasbiy taraqqiyoti motivatsiyasining psixologik xususiyatlari	78
<i>Rustamova Surayyo Shaxobiddinovna</i>	
Innovatsion kompetentlik tushunchasi va uning ilmiy-pedagogik asoslari.....	84
<i>Soliyev Eliyor Ravshan o'g'li</i>	
Nutqida nuqsoni bo'lgan bolalar eshituv idrokini o'yinlar yordamida rivojlantirishning samarali usullari	88
<i>Xalilova Shahnoza</i>	
Zamonaviy ta'limda kommunikativ kompetensiyaning o'rni va ahamiyati.....	92
<i>Yaqubova Nigoraxon Ibrohimjon qizi</i>	
Soliq yuki – mamlakat soliq soliq tizimining asosiy mezonidir	97
<i>Suyunov Otabek Shuxrat o'g'li</i>	
Bo'lajak o'qituvchilarda kasbiy kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirish va takomillashtirish yo'llari	101
<i>Ibodova Sarvinoz Sayfilloyevna</i>	
Oliy ta'lim muassasalarida hospital pedagogika fanini o'qitishning dolzarb masalalari va uning uslubiy ta'minoti	106
<i>Inogamova Dilfuza Rahmatullaevna</i>	

Chizma geometriya va kompyuter grafikasi: an'anaviy fan va zamonaviy texnologiyaning uyg'unlashuvi .	111
<i>Raximov A. M., Tairova N. S., Sabirova D. U., Xasanova S. T., Tashpulatov R. X.</i>	
Геймификация в обучении английскому языку на начальном этапе обучения	114
<i>Курбанова Назира Низомиддиновна</i>	
Talabalarda tanqidiy va evristik fikrlashni shakllantirishda raqamli texnologiyalarning o'rni	117
<i>Adjdiyev Nayrullo Nazrulloevich</i>	
Konstruktiv yondashuv asosida tabiiy fanlar (science)ni o'qitish metodikasi.....	122
<i>Amirullayeva Barno Abdulhaqovna</i>	
Kimyo o'qitishda o'quvchilarning ijodiy faoliyatini shakllantirishning tajriba-sinov natijalari.....	126
<i>Artiqov Maqsud Bahodirovich, Babanazarova Ayzada Omirbaevna</i>	
Kichik maktab yoshidagi o'quvchilarni bilingvist sifatida shakllantirishda til o'rganish ko'nikmalari va kompetentsiyalarining rivojlanishi	131
<i>Axmadjonova Gulira'no Muxtorjon qizi</i>	
Talabalarning ijtimoiy kompetensiyalarini shakllantirishda kooperativ ta'limning metodik yondashuvlari.....	135
<i>Botiraliyeva Gulobar Mahamadismoil qizi</i>	
Talabalarni intellektual faoliyatga tayyorlashda ijtimoiy sherikchilikning pedagogik va metodik asoslari	139
<i>Dilbarjonov Avazbek Ravshanbek o'g'li</i>	
Teacher-Centered and Child-Centered Methods in Early Childhood Education: Insights From Finland and Uzbekistan	143
<i>Djaparova Gulnoza</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarida "Metodik mahorat kuni" va "Metodik mahorat soati"ni tashkil etish	150
<i>Do'stov Davron Zulhaydarovich</i>	
Theoretical, Methodological, and Practical Factors of Differentiated Education	155
<i>Ergash Shonazarovich Khasanov</i>	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarning intellektual qobiliyatini rivojlantirishda kognitiv yondoshuv	160
<i>Gulbahor Xamidova</i>	
Mustaqil ta'lim – mustahkam bilim.....	164
<i>Halima Shukurova Sunatullayevna</i>	
Integrating Google Classroom and Project-Based Learning for Enhanced Synchronous and Asynchronous Education.....	168
<i>Inomkhojaeva Shodiyakhon Abdukodirkhoja qizi</i>	
O'quvchilarning innovatsion fikrlash ko'nikmalarini takomillashtirishning nazariy asoslari.....	174
<i>Mamadaliyev Axadjon G'aniboyevich</i>	
Hududiy rivojlanishda innovatsion yondashuvlarni strategik boshqaruvga integratsiya qilish yo'llari.....	177
<i>Mo'minov Fazliddin Xusniddin o'g'li</i>	
O'rta yoshdagi ayollarda harakat faoliyatini rivojlantirishda milliy o'yinlarning pedagogik ahamiyati	184
<i>Mustafoev Sherali</i>	
Pedagogical and Psychological Foundations of Developing Higher-Order Thinking Skills in Students.....	188
<i>Nasimova Zarina Isomiddin kizi</i>	
Pedagogik ijodkorlikning kasbiy professionallikda namoyon bo'lish xususiyatlari.....	193
<i>Numonova Dildor Umurzoqovna</i>	
Ko'zi oqiz boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining kommunikativ kompetentsiyasini o'rganishning nazariy asoslari	196
<i>Qarshiboyev Asliddin</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarida ta'lim-tarbiya jarayonini tashkil etish masalalari.....	200
<i>Qilichova Marxabo Xudayqulovna</i>	
The Transformation of Existential Thought in British Literature: Iris Murdoch's Philosophical Humanism and the Reinterpretation of Freedom	204
<i>Rahmonqulova Zarnigor Nasimjon qizi</i>	
Sportchilarning elektron platformalardan foydalanishning metodik tahlili	209
<i>Saydullayev Zafar Erkinovich</i>	
Adabiy ta'limda estetik tarbiya	216
<i>Sharipov Elmurod Sa'dulla o'g'li</i>	
O'qituvchi-trenerning ko'p qirrali kasbiy-pedagogik funksiyalari	220
<i>Sulaymonov Jaxongir Solijonovich</i>	
Uzluksiz kasbiy rivojlanishda art-pedagogikaning o'qituvchilar hissiy farovonligiga ta'siri	223
<i>Suvanova Kamola Raimqul qizi</i>	

Raqamlashtirish muhitida umumta'lim maktablarida ta'lim sifatini oshirish	226
<i>Xamidova Komila Maxmudovna</i>	
Oliy ta'limda kvest texnologiyasi yordamida fizika fanining murakkab tushunchalarini o'zlashtirish samaradorligini oshirish metodikasi.....	231
<i>Yo'ichiyev Shaxriyor Xusanovich, O'rinboyeva Kumushoy Sultonbek qizi</i>	
Совершенствование профессиональных компетенций будущих инженеров на основе интегративного подхода	235
<i>Умарова Гулчехра Абитовна</i>	
Kichik maktab yoshidagi o'quvchilarning aqliy qobiliyatining psixologik xususiyatlari	238
<i>Alanazarova Sholpan Artikbaevna, Artiqbaeva Miyassar Jumanazarovna</i>	
Biologiya ta'limida innovatsion metodlarni joriy etishda ta'lim menejmentining roli.....	241
<i>Allayorova Maloxat Normaxmat qizi</i>	
Integrating Innovative Technologies for the Enhancement of Speech and Communication Skills Among Learners With Intellectual Disabilities in Uzbekistan: Pedagogical Approaches and Developmental Outcomes	244
<i>Donisheva Gulruy Akhrorkulovna</i>	
Bo'lajak boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarini o'quvchilar o'qish savodxonligini rivojlantirishga metodik jihatdan tayyorlash.....	247
<i>Doniyarov Mavlonbek Arabovich</i>	
Kimyoviy birikmalarda bog'lar sonini hisoblashning yangi matematik usullari.....	252
<i>Ergashev Vahob Ergashevich</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarining mantiqiy tafakkurini rivojlantirish pedagogik muammo sifatida	257
<i>G'aniyeva Maftuna Abduaziz qizi</i>	
Pedagogika oliy o'quv yurtlarida steam fanlarini raqamli texnologiyalar asosida o'qitishning metodik asoslari	261
<i>Jamolova Sitara Muzaffar qizi</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining matematik tafakkurini rivojlantirishda didaktik o'yinlar va interaktiv metodlardan foydalanish samaradorligi	264
<i>Mamadiyurov Jamol</i>	
Zamonaviy ta'lim jarayonida talabalar mustaqil faoliyatini rivojlantirishda pedagogik yondashuvlar.....	268
<i>Mamayusupova Nafisa Abdulatifovna</i>	
Para yengil atletikachilarda nayza uloqtirish texnikasini takomillashtirish uslubiyati	271
<i>Qiyomova Shohsanam Yarash qizi</i>	
Difficulties in Enhancing Communicativeness of Pre-Service English Teachers.....	275
<i>Kurbonova Maftuna Fakhriddinovna, Mirzayeva Gulshan Azamatovna</i>	
Principles of Teaching Basic Foreign Language Skills (EFL)	278
<i>Samandarova Gulsara Ismatilloevna</i>	
O'quvchilarning innovatsion ta'lim muhitida tayanch kompetensiyalarini shakllantirishning dolzarbligi	282
<i>Toshpulatova Farida Radjabovna</i>	
Корпоративная культура педагогов и внутренняя стабильность ДОО	286
<i>Буранова Шохноза Абдуразаковна</i>	
Развивать личностные качества учащихся на уроках географии.....	290
<i>Шадиева Нигора Шариповна</i>	
Raqamli texnologiyalar yordamida oliy ta'lim sifatini oshirishda innovatsion yondashuvlar	295
<i>Baytileuova Gulnaz Quralbay qizi</i>	
Yangi avlod pedagoglarini tayyorlash: kompetensiyalar va qadriyatlarining roli.....	298
<i>Ro'ziboyeva Ma'mura Abdunabiyevna</i>	
Astronomiya fanini o'qitishda integrativ yondashuvdan foydalanib o'qitishning ta'lim tizimidagi o'rni	301
<i>Barakayeva Sarvinoz To'iqunovna</i>	
Alohida e'tiborga muhtoj bolalar bilan ishlashda yangi pedagogik texnologiyalarni qo'llash.....	305
<i>Usmonov Salohiddin Dushan o'g'li, Namozova Sevinch Asqar qizi</i>	
Ma'naviy-axloqiy sifatlarni tarbiyalashda pedagogik qadriyatlarining ustuvorligi.....	310
<i>Jumayeva Gulnara Tursunpulatovna</i>	
Talabalarni maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarini maqsadli boshqarishga tayyorlashning nazariy asoslari	314
<i>Mahmudova Zulfiya Xomitovna</i>	
Pedagogical Methodology Improve Students' Professional Mobility in Acquisition of Specialty.....	319
<i>Khidirova Muhabbat Murodillayevna</i>	

Boshlang'ich sinf ona tili darslarida pedagogik texnologiyalardan foydalanish	322
<i>Ismoilova Surmaxon Amonovna, Yusupova Mohinur</i>	
Qoraqalpoqlarning dehqonchilik marosimlari	326
<i>Orinboyeva Go'zal Polatovna</i>	
The Complexity of Training Teaching Staff for Work in Public Schools Organized in Medical Stations in Uzbekistan.....	330
<i>Inogamova Dilfuza Rakhmatullaevna</i>	
Boshlang'ich ta'lim texnologiya fanini o'qitishda STEM yondashuvi orqali o'quvchilarda mustaqil va tanqidiy fikrlash ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish.....	335
<i>Jabbarova Zuhra Omondullayevna</i>	
Eshitishda nuqsoni mavjud bolalarni nutqini shakllantirish metodikasi	338
<i>Z. N. Mamarajabova</i>	
5–7-sinf qizlarida raqamli texnologiyalar ta'sirida tarbiya jarayonining o'ziga xosliklari.....	341
<i>Abdurazoqova Marg'uba Muhammad qizi</i>	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda emotsional intellektni rivojlantirish diagnostikasi: metodlar va natijalar ..	345
<i>Abduxamidova Dilorom Abdumuminovna</i>	
PISA topshiriqlari asosida o'quvchilarda tadqiqotchilik ko'nikmalarini shakllantirish	349
<i>Axunjanova Shirmonoy Isroiljonovna</i>	
Bo'lajak surdotarjimonlar uchun faoliyat turlarini tanlashda ko'maklashish	354
<i>Dehqanova Muborakxon G'iyosiddinovna</i>	
Mustaqil ta'limni tashkillashtirishda tarjimadan foydalanish jarayonlari	357
<i>Erkayev Elmira Temirovich</i>	
Bo'lajak boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarining kasbiy faoliyat samaradorligini oshirishda kreativ va tanqidiy fikrlash kompetensiyalarining o'rni.....	361
<i>Jumayeva Muxlisa Shokir qizi</i>	
Tasks, Exercises, and Activities in the English Classroom: Differences, Similarities, and Effective Use	366
<i>Qodirov Olim Odilovich</i>	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda kommunikativ kompetentlikni rivojlantirish masalalari	372
<i>Safarova Mohichehra Xonzafarovna</i>	
Malaka oshirish tizimida boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarini tabiiy-ilmiy savodxonligini rivojlantirish masalalari.....	376
<i>Saidova Dilnoza Maripovna</i>	
O'zbekiston va Yaponiya dzyudo trenerlarining mashg'ulot jarayonlarini qiyosiy tahlili.....	380
<i>Sharipov Xabibullo Abduqahhorovich</i>	
"Kompyuter lingvistikasi"ning rivojlanish tendensiyasi.....	386
<i>Xusanboyeva Muxlisa Ikrojon qizi</i>	
Педагогические технологии стратегического развития взаимного сотрудничества организаций дошкольного образования и родителей.....	392
<i>Тухлиев Муслимбек Шерзод угли</i>	
Oliy ta'limda inklyuziv ta'lim tizimini joriy etish muammolari	397
<i>Dilbar Nurkeldiyeva</i>	
Ixtisoslashtirilgan ta'lim muasasalarida tarbiyaning o'rni.....	401
<i>Laylo Sharopovna Nurmuxamedova</i>	
Intellektida kamchiligi bo'lgan bolalarning ijtimoiylashuvida muloqotning shakllanish xususiyatlari.....	405
<i>Shahnoza Amirsaidova</i>	
Aqli zaif bolalarga ta'lim jarayonida o'yin faoliyatini shakllantirishning ahamiyati.....	409
<i>Ziyodullayeva E'zoza Ne'matjonovna</i>	
Pedagogik texnologiyalar metodlarini tanlash va qo'llashning umumiy mezonlari	412
<i>Abdullayeva Komila Tursunovna</i>	
Didaktik o'yinlar vositasida 2-sinf o'quvchilarida bog'lanishli nutq ko'nikmalarini shakllantirishning pedagogik imkoniyatlari	416
<i>Askarova Gulayim Arislan qizi</i>	
Yugurib kelib uzunlikka sakrovchilarda tezkorlikni samarali va jadal rivojlantirishni ilmiy asoslash.....	420
<i>Avazov Shukrullo Ibatovich, Nuraliyeva O'g'iloy Shomurotovna, Mustafayev Ismoil Nuralio'g'li</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinflarda kreativ ta'limning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari va zaruriyati.....	425
<i>Axmedova Mastura Jamoliddinovna</i>	
Imkoniyati cheklangan o'quvchilarda tabiatshunoslik kompetensiyasini shakllantirishning pedagogik shart-sharoitlari	430
<i>Azizova Dilnora</i>	

Bo'lajak shifokorlarda tibbiy – deontologik kompetensiyalarni shakllanishida tibbiy amaliyotning ahamiyati.....	435
Babadjanova Gulchexra Baxtiyarovna	
Bolaning aqliy rivojlanishini yoritadigan ko'rsatkichlar	440
Bozorboyev Javlon Davlatali o'g'li	
Bo'lajak oligofrenopedagoglarning kasbiy-metodik kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirish xususiyatlari.....	445
Daminova Maftuna Asqarali qizi	
Kreativ pedagogika fani va mantiqiy fikrlash kompetentligi orasidagi bog'liqlik.....	449
Diyora Egamberdiyeva	
Oilani mustahkamlovchi va ajralishiga olib keluvchi omillar	454
Haqberdiyev Jamoliddin Abdug'affor o'g'li	
Quality Management as a Functional and Attributive Characteristic of Modern Management.....	458
Jabbarbergenova Bibimaryam Amangeldievna	
Bo'lajak boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarining ijodiy faoliyatini rivojlantirishda pedagogik va psixologik jarayonlar	464
Mamedova Maxfuza Erkinovna	
Huquqiy ong va madaniyatni shakllantirishda yuridik ta'limning roli: tahlil va takliflar	470
Mansurova Zilola Akromxonovna	
Pedagogik ta'limda klaster yondashuvi: O'zbekiston va jahon tajribasi	474
Nafisa Tokhirova Dilshod qizi	
Bo'lajak boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarining kasbiy kompetentligini rivojlantirishning nazariy-pedagogik asoslari: zamonaviy yondashuvlar va innovatsion imkoniyatlarning integratsiyasi asosida shakllanish jarayoni.....	478
Norqulov Lutfullo Mamarajabovich	
Montessori metodikasi va undagi bolalar sensomotorikasini rivojlantirishga doir tajribalar tahlili	484
Parmonova Laylo Iloxomovna	
Molekulyar fizikani modellashtirish orqali o'qitish metodikasini takomillashtirish.....	488
Q. U. Tog'ayeva	
Milliy tarbiyada raqamli vositalardan foydalanishning pedagogik imkoniyatlari	493
Qo'shnazarova Nozima Maxmutjon qizi	
Learning Intercultural Communication Through Social Media: the Approach of Modern Students	498
Raxmonqulova Feruza Akmal qizi	
Aqliy rivojlanishda muammolari bor maktab o'quvchilarida geometrik tushunchalarni shakllantirishning nazariy asoslar.....	502
Shodiyeva Navbaxor Xabibulla qizi	
Logopedning kasbiy faoliyatida deontologiya va kompetentlikning roli va ahamiyati	506
Temurova Gulchexra Xudoqulovna, Isomitdinova Shaxinabonu Zavqiddin qizi	
STEAM ta'limida lego konstrukturlarining o'rni va ahamiyati.....	511
Toshpulatova Farida Radjabovna	
Diagnostikasi va rehabilitatsiya qilishda eshitishda nuqsoni bo'lgan bola va ularning ota-onalari bilan bog'liq muammolar.....	514
Toshpulova Nodira Sultonmurod qizi	
Talabalarni maktabgacha ta'lim tashkiloti va ota-onalar hamkorligi o'rtasidagi o'zaro munosabat shakllari.....	518
Turdiqulova Luiza Zayniddinovna	
O'zbekistonda ESG tamoyillarining ta'limga integratsiyasi: yutuqlar, muammolar va istiqbollari	522
Tursunova Shahzoda Baxromovna	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi aqli zaif bolalarning fazoviy tasavvurlarini shakllantirish	526
Xamidova Muyassar Polsaidovna	
Mustaqil ta'limni tashkil etishning asosiy didaktik prinsiplari.....	530
Yuldashev Shukrullo	
Комплексная методика развития и обучения юных футболистов	536
Ортиков Умиджон Худойбердиевич	
Особенности деятельности детей с нарушением зрения	544
Юсупова Назира	
Integration of Music and Language: Creative Approaches to Teaching English to Music Students	548
Akbarova Moxichexra	

Ingliz tilida yozuv malakalarini takomillashtirishda baholash metodikasi.....	553
<i>Alimardonova Malika Botir qizi</i>	
Yosh kurashchilarni jismoniy va aqliy rivojlantirishda basketbol o'yinining ahamiyati	560
<i>Haqnazarov Qurbon Qo'shayevich</i>	
Voleybol murabbiylarining innovatsion fikrlash qobiliyatini shakllantirish usullari	566
<i>Haqqulov Akbar Abdiraupovich</i>	
Sociolinguistic Competence and Intercultural Communicative Competence: Intertwining Concepts and Practical Implications	571
<i>Kuchmurodova Gulnora Khatamovna</i>	
Ilk qadam davlat dasturida steam ta'lim elementlaridan foydalanish imkoniyati	575
<i>Nazarova Aziza Sohib qizi</i>	
Kasbiy rivojlanish jarayonida rahbar shaxsiy sifatlarini rivojlantirishning zamonaviy yo'nalishlari.....	579
<i>Roziqova Nazokat Alisher qizi</i>	
Deontologik yondashuvning nazariy-pedagogik asoslari va uning ta'lim tizimidagi ahamiyati	583
<i>Tashpulatova Nodira Olimjon qizi</i>	
Kasbiy-pedagogik tayyorgarlikda fanlararo integratsiya asosida boshlang'ich ta'lim yo'nalishi o'qituvchilarining metodik salohiyatini oshirish yo'llari.....	586
<i>Xashimova Aziza Alisherovna</i>	
Природа и механизм действия биологических иммуностимуляторов на организм животных	590
<i>Койилова Мехринисо Джураевна</i>	
Badiiy asarlar ustida ishlash jarayonida boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining emotsional intellektini shakllantirish mezonlari	594
<i>Jamalova Kamola Shahobiddinovna</i>	
Bo'lajak o'qituvchilarning tanqidiy fikrlashini rivojlantirish asosida fizika o'qitish metodikasini takomillashtirish	600
<i>Musurmonova Shaxnoza Dilshod qizi</i>	
Futbolchilarda texnik tayyorgarlikni takomillashtirishning ilmiy-metodik asoslari.....	606
<i>Babayev Anvarjon Axmedovich</i>	
Semantik afaziya va uni bartaraf etish yo'llari	611
<i>Umida O'tabasarova Mexmanovna, G'anieva Gulrux Tavakkaljon qizi</i>	
Сравнительный анализ национальных видов борьбы Японии.....	616
<i>Даминов Илхом Аширралиевич</i>	
Pedagogik jarayonda kognitiv rivojlanishga ta'sir qiluvchi omillar va bu faoliyatni rivojlantiruvchi interaktiv metodlar va texnologiyalar	621
<i>Abdiraimova Gulrux Samad qizi</i>	
Aqli zaif kichik maktab yoshidagi bolalarda o'qishni o'zlashtirishga motivatsion tayyorlikni shakllantirish ...	625
<i>Abdunazarov Abdumutal Olimovich, Xaitboyeva Kumushxon Farxodjon qizi</i>	
Psixik rivojlanishida kechikishi bo'lgan bolalar nutqini rivojlantirishda neyrokorreksiya mashg'ulotlarning ahamiyati	628
<i>Akramova Xafiza Samadovna, Jumanova Mashhura Shokir qizi</i>	
Pedagogik amaliyotning bo'lajak o'qituvchilar tayyorlash tizimidagi o'rni	632
<i>Aliyeva Mavjudaxon Baxromjon qizi</i>	
O'zbek tili darslarida media matnlardan foydalanish usullari.....	637
<i>Allakhova Bagdagul Djoldasbayevna</i>	
Media axborot vositalarining bolalar va o'smir yoshlarga ta'siri.....	640
<i>Arobova Shohsanam Akram qizi</i>	
Biologiya ta'limida tizimli-faoliyatli yondashuvning nazariy-metodologik asoslari.....	645
<i>Asrorova Odinaoy Otabek qizi</i>	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi dizartirik bolalarning so'z boyligini rivojlantirish yo'llari	650
<i>Azizova Nilyufar Mirziyadovna</i>	
Ijtimoiy pedagog faoliyatida innovatsion yondashuvlar	656
<i>Bahriddinova Gavhar Oydinovna</i>	
Ta'lim tizimida deontologik yondashuvlarning pedagogik imoniyatlari.....	659
<i>Boboxujayev Johonmirzo Umar o'g'li</i>	
Zamonaviy ta'limda imkoniyati cheklangan bolalarga nisbatan inklyuziv yondashuv.....	662
<i>Djurayeva Hurshida</i>	
Libos va aksessuarlar orqali milliy estetik didni shakllantirishning pedagogik mexanizmlari	666
<i>Doniyorova Shahnoza Erkin qizi</i>	

MUNDARIJA СОДЕРЖАНИЕ CONTENTS	Mantiqiy fikrlashni rivojlantiruvchi mashg'ulotlarni tashkil etish bosqichlari mazmuni 672 Dosbayeva Shahnoza Abdurahimovna
	Maktabgacha ta'lim yoshidagi bolalarga chet tili o'rgatishning pedagogik-psixologik asoslari 675 Ergasheva Xilola Yunusxonovna
	Use of Artificial Intelligence in Teaching English as a Foreign Language for Uzbekistan General Schools 679 Feruz Zokirova Adham qizi
	Efferent motor afaziya va uni bartaraf etish yo'llari 682 G'anieva Gulrux Tavakkaljon qizi
	O'quvchilarda ekologik kompetensiyani shakllantirish: biologiya darslarida global ekologik muammolar tahlili 686 Ibragimova Sitora Akmal qizi
	Ba'zi 3D-metallarining 2-amino-5-allitio-1,3,4-tiadiazol bilan kompleks birikmalarini o'rganish 690 Jumaniyazova Gulxumar Karimbayevna
	Tizimli bilish kompetentligining mazmuni va uning maktabgacha ta'limdagi o'rni 696 Mirazimova Muxabbat Normatovna
	O'qituvchilik mahorati va axloqiy madaniyatning mushtarakligi 700 Nabiyev Islom Karimovich
	Qarshi shahrida turizm menejerlarining kasbiy malakasini uzluksiz takomillashtirishni ta'minlash 706 Normurodova Zebo Eshmaxmatovna
	Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida moslashuvchan kompetensiyalarni shakllantirishning metodik asoslari 710 Nuriddinova Diyora Isaqali qizi
	Mediasavodxonlik vositasida bo'lajak boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarining tanqidiy fikrlashini rivojlantirishning pedagogik xususiyatlari 714 Pardayev Asror Ikromovich
	Boshlang'ich sinf ona tili darslarida kommunikativ kompetensiyalarni shakllantirish metodikasi 718 Qayumova Mahfuzaxon Alisher qizi
	Yuqori sinf o'quvchilarining ma'naviy kompetentligini jadidlarning pedagogik qarashlari asosida shakllantirish metodikasi (Temurbeklar maktablari misolida) 724 Quldashv Murodjon G'aniyevich
	Bugungi voleybolda to'p uzatish texnikasi va aniqligini 13–14 yoshdan boshlab aylanish harakatlari ta'sirida shakllantirish afzalligi 727 Rejapov O'tkirbek G'ayratjon o'g'li
	Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilariga bolalar o'yin folklorini o'rgatishda tolerantlikni rivojlantirishning metodik usullari va texnologiyalari 733 Ro'ziboyeva Madina Salimovna
	Pedagogik muloqot tushunchasi va uning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari 737 Ro'zimatova Maxpuza
	Intellektual qadriyatlarning talaba yoshlar aksiologik hayotiy pozitsiyasini shakllantirishdagi roli 743 Rustam Latipov Mamadaliyevich
	Bo'lajak tasviriy san'at o'qituvchilarini tayyorlashda AI-platformalarni integratsiyalashning amaliy mexanizmlari 747 Rustamov Kamoliddin Ziyodillo o'g'li
	Maktab biologiya ta'limida individuallashtirish texnologiyasidan foydalanish metodikasi 754 Savutova Malohat Erkinovna
	Bo'lajak o'qituvchilarning turizm sohasiga bo'lgan munosabatini o'rganishning ijtimoiy-pedagogik metodikasi 760 Shodiyorov Rustam Xasan o'g'li
	Bo'lajak harbiy xizmatchilarda deontologik yondashuvlar asosida raqamli muloqot madaniyatini shakllantirish 764 Soyibnazarov Baxtiyor Abdunazar o'g'li
	Pedagogika oliy o'quv yurtlarida umumiy yer bilimi fanidan amaliy mashg'ulotlar tizimini kasbiy faoliyatga yo'naltirishning dolzarb masalalari 770 Sultanova N. B.
	Ijtimoiy reabilitatsiyani amalga oshirishda tibbiy-psixokorreksion maslahat ishlar mazmuni 775 Suvanqulova Shaxnoza Karimqulovna
	Blokcheyn texnologiyasining ta'lim jarayonida qo'llanilishi va imkoniyatlari 780 Suyumov Jo'rabek Yunusaliyevich

Oila va xotin-qizlar tizimida kollaborativ madaniyatning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari	783
<i>Tojibayeva Nazokatxon</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining tafakkurini rivojlantirishda interfaol metodlarning o'rni	787
<i>To'xtasinova Nigoraxon Azizxon qizi</i>	
Oliy o'quv yurtlarida analitik kimyo fanini o'qitishning samaradorlik ko'rsatkichlari	793
<i>Umrbekova Maftuna Ulug'bek qizi</i>	
Antroposentrik yondashuv asosida o'quvchilarda insonparvarlik fazilatlarini shakllantirish yo'llari	796
<i>Xamidova Nigora Ibrohimovna</i>	
Обучение говорению на русском языке абитуриентов с помощью настольных игр	800
<i>Абдулахадова Шохида</i>	
Особенности педагогической деятельности и их виды	803
<i>Мавжудова Ш. С., Мирходжаева Д.</i>	
Развитие критического мышления младших школьников на уроках читательской грамотности	808
<i>Мухаммадиева Марифат Мурод кизи</i>	
Искусство подбора слов: стилистические и семантические возможности перифраз	811
<i>Юлдашева Дилноза Бекмуродовна</i>	
Zamonaviy pedagogik texnologiyalar asosida talabalarda reflektiv tafakkurni rivojlantirishning vazifalari va pedagogik imkoniyatlari	815
<i>Abdullayeva Ziroatxon Qurbonovna</i>	
The Human Factor in AI-Mediated English Instruction: Balancing Technology and Pedagogical Expertise	818
<i>Ikramova Aziza Aminovna</i>	
Madaniyat tushunchasi va uni xorijiy til o'qitishda o'rganish zarurati	823
<i>Ma'murova Farangiz Ne'matovna</i>	
O'quvchilarda tanqidiy tafakkurni shakllantirish: zamonaviy pedagogik yondashuvlar va ularning samaradorligi	827
<i>Ostonova Ma'mura Ulug'bek qizi</i>	
Ko'zi oqib boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining kommunikativ kompetentsiyasini o'rganishning nazariy asoslari	830
<i>Qarshiboyev Asiddin</i>	
Farzand tarbiyasida ota-onaning pedagogik-psixologik malakalari	834
<i>Xojimirzayeva Shaxnoza Shokir qizi</i>	
Darsdan tashqari mashg'ulotlarda o'quvchilarni kasb-hunarga yo'llashning tashkiliy-ilmiy asoslari	839
<i>Xolmatov Pardaboy Qoraboevich</i>	
Методология типологического и сравнительного анализа детского фольклора	844
<i>Азмиева Э. Э.</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'lim elementar matematik tushunchalarni rivojlantirish zarurati	851
<i>Xoldarova F. M.</i>	
Multimadaniy muhitda pedagoglarning tanqidiy fikrlash ko'nikmalarini shakllantirish mexanizmlari	854
<i>Gulyamova Nafisa Burikulovna</i>	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda milliy qadriyat tushunchalarini shakllantirishda oila va mahallaning roli	858
<i>Rizayeva Xusniya Ubayevna</i>	
Raqamli pedagogika: zamonaviy ta'limda innovatsion texnologiyalar roli	861
<i>Maxmudova Dilnoza Xaytmirzaevna</i>	
Badiiy adabiyot – maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda estetik dunyoqarashni shakllantiruvchi omil sifatida	865
<i>Xujamberdiyeva Shahnoza Kupaysinovna</i>	
Yangi O'zbekistonda inklyuziv ta'lim islohatlar bosqichida	868
<i>Boyqulov Azamat Maxram o'g'li</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlari direktor o'rinbosarlarining menejerlik ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishning xorijiy tajribasi va uni mahalliy sharoitda qo'llash imkoniyatlari	871
<i>Maxamadaliyeva Ezoza Rustamxo'ja qizi</i>	
Oliy badiiy pedagogik ta'lim muassasasida bo'lajak tasviriy san'at o'qituvchilarini maktab o'quvchilarida illyustrativ rasm ishlashga oid kompetensiyalarini shakllantirishga tayyorlashning mazmuni	875
<i>Sobirov Sarvar Tursunmurotovich</i>	
Kasb-hunar maktablarida fizika fanini steam integratsiyasi asosida o'qitishning nazariy-didaktik asoslari	878
<i>Mamatxonov Yorkin Abduraimjanovich, Soliyeva Mubinabonu Zokirjon qizi</i>	
Inklyuziv ta'lim sharoitida olib boriladigan pedagogik faoliyat imkoniyatlari	885
<i>Abidova Nilufar Zakirovna</i>	

Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarida tarbiyalanuvchilarni kasbga yo'naltirish: pedagogik yondashuvlar va amaliy tajribalar.....	888
<i>Ahmedova Lola Abdivasi qizi</i>	
Aqli zaif o'quvchilarni ijtimoiy-maishiy kompetensiyasini shakllantirishning asosiy komponentlari va samarali omillari.....	893
<i>Anvarova Dilfuza Akramjanovna</i>	
O'quv topshiriqlari orqali 6-sinf o'quvchilarining pragmatik kompetensiyasini rivojlantirishning ilmiy-metodologik asoslari.....	896
<i>Ashirboyeva Nafisa Aminboyevna</i>	
Talabalarda ijtimoiy faollik ko'nikmalarini takomillashtirish va uning amaliy ahamiyati.....	900
<i>Ergasheva Maftunaxon Avazbekovna</i>	
Talabalarda zamonaviy pedagogik texnologiyalar asosida reflektiv tafakkurni rivojlantirish.....	904
<i>Ergasheva Nigora Dilshodjon qizi</i>	
Maktabgacha katta yoshdagi bolalarni kasbga qiziqishlarini rivojlantirishning pedagogik va psixologik xususiyatlari.....	907
<i>Isabekova Dilafuz Shermirzayevna, Gazibekova Gulvaza Ergashovna</i>	
Innovatsion ta'lim texnologiyalarini qo'llashning nazariy asoslari.....	913
<i>Murodov Akmal Djayliboyevich</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'lim yoshdagi intellektida nuqsoni bo'lgan bolalarning estetik muomala madaniyatini tarbiyalash.....	917
<i>Po'latova Parida</i>	
Fizika fanini o'qitishda raqamli ta'lim vositalarining samaradorligi.....	920
<i>Saparova Gulmira Baxtiyorovna</i>	
Rus tilini o'qitishda an'anaviy va audiovizual usullarning qiyosiy tahlili.....	923
<i>Umarov Aziz Avazovich</i>	
An Analysis of The Importance of Teaching English at the Primary Level.....	927
<i>Vasila Almetova Sunnatullayevna</i>	
Muammoli ta'lim texnologiyalarini ta'lim jarayonida qo'llash.....	931
<i>Adizova Nodira Baxtiyorovna</i>	
"Informatika va axborot texnologiyalari" fanidan iqtidorli o'quvchilar bilan ishlashning ilmiy-pedagogik yondashuvlari.....	936
<i>Akmaljon Xushvaqtov</i>	
Iqtidorli talabalar bilan ishlash pedagogik muammolari.....	939
<i>Delov To'liqin Erkinovich</i>	
Rinolaliya nutq nuqsonining anatomik jihatdan kelib chiqishi.....	945
<i>Kabirova Zarnigor Raxmonjon qizi</i>	
Methodology for Teaching Modal Verbs in English Lessons.....	949
<i>Kholnazarova Vazira Bozor qizi</i>	
The Use of Mobile Apps to Build Vocabulary Proficiency.....	953
<i>Kosimov Sunnat Ravshan ugli</i>	
Disability Terminology in Uzbek: Etymological Evolution and Future Trends.....	957
<i>Kuchkarova Xurshida</i>	
Bo'lajak muhandislarni grafik dasturlar yordamida loyihaviy-konstruktorlik kompetentligini rivojlantirish (muhandislik va kompyuter grafikasi fani misolida).....	964
<i>Madaminov Javlonbek Zafarjonovich</i>	
Ijodiy tafakkurni rivojlantirishda interaktiv darsliklarning pedagogik imkoniyatlari.....	968
<i>Mirzaakbarov Dilshod Davlatboyevich</i>	
Sog'lom turmush tarzi – jismoniy madaniyati sohibi sifatida jismoniy mashqlar komplekslarini tuzish va bajarishda amal qilinadigan qoidalar.....	971
<i>Musayev Zarifjon Tursunaliyevich</i>	
Bo'lajak defektologlarning pedagogik mas'uliyatini oshirish.....	974
<i>Nodira Mirboboyeva</i>	
Bo'lajak o'qituvchilarni kreativ yondashuv asosida innovatsion faoliyatga tayyorlash texnologiyasini takomillashtirish modeli.....	977
<i>Odamboyeva Mehrimon Norimon qizi</i>	
O'quvchini muloqot qilish ko'nikmalarini shakllantirishda kitobxonlikning o'rni.....	981
<i>Qurbanova O'g'iloy Axrorovna</i>	

Sharq mutafakkirlari asarlari vositasida boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining ijtimoiy faollik ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishning afzalliklari.....	985
<i>Rejabboyeva Muxarram Odiljon qizi</i>	
Pedagogik ta'lim jarayonida raqamli nazorat tizimlaridan foydalanish samaradorligi va rivojlantirish yo'nalishlari	989
<i>Samijonov Azizbek Ismoiljon o'g'li</i>	
Dizartriya nutq kamchiligini bartaraf etishda muassasa, logoped va oilaning hamkorligi.....	992
<i>Shermatova Yukut Sabirovna</i>	
Kulolchilik va an'anaviy o'yinchoqlarni o'quvchilar kasb tanlash jarayonida qo'llash metodikasi	995
<i>Soliyeva Diyora Bobur qizi</i>	
O'zbekistonda inkluziv ta'lim va uning me'yoriy-huquqiy asoslari	998
<i>Temirov Nabijon Soliyevich, Esonova Klaraxon Mahmamin qizi</i>	
Oila va xotin-qizlar tizimida kollaborativ madaniyatning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari	1001
<i>Tojibayeva Nazokatxon</i>	
Sun'iy intellekt yordamida talaffuz va tinglab tushunish ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish metodikasi	1005
<i>Tojiyev Olimjon Haqberdi o'g'li</i>	
Boshlang'ich ta'lim tizimi muammo va istiqbollari sotsiologik tadqiqotlar asosida.....	1008
<i>Voxidova Muqaddas Rasuljon qizi</i>	
Oliy ta'lim talabalarida integrativ yondashuv asosida tanqidiy fikrlash kompetentligini rivojlantirish metodikasi	1011
<i>Xalimova Mashraboy Vaxidovna, Botirova Mavluda To'xtasin qizi</i>	
5–6 yoshli bolalarda ekologik madaniyatni rivojlantirishda o'yinli texnologiyalarini qo'llashning pedagogik shart-sharoitlari	1015
<i>Xolboyeva Gulnora Ulashovna, Dolliyeva Xayrigul Namoz qizi</i>	
Bo'lajak tarbiyachilarda kasbiy kompetentlikning namoyon bo'lishi psixologik fenomen sifatida	1018
<i>Xoshimova Y. I.</i>	
Inklyuziv ta'lim sharoitida pedagogik va psixologik yondashuvlarning mazmuni.....	1023
<i>Xudoyqulova Aziza Anvar qizi</i>	
Pedagogik ta'limda mediakompetentlikni shakllantirish jarayonida raqamli resurslardan foydalanish samaradorligi.....	1026
<i>Yuldashov Sherzod Sattorovich</i>	
Особенности развития эмоционального интеллекта у дошкольников	1029
<i>Жамолова Зарнигор Баходир кизи</i>	
Стратегии лингвистического моделирования в обучении русскому языку и их роль в формировании идентичности студентов.....	1033
<i>Рузметова Наргиза Ахмедовна, Рузметова Хилола Абдушориповна</i>	
Bo'lajak boshlang'ich ta'lim o'qituvchilarini matematik mushohada yuritishga o'rgatish	1038
<i>Dehqonova Mahliyo Shuhrat qizi</i>	
Tarbiyachi inklyuziv kompetentligi va zamonaviy ta'limda uning o'rni.....	1041
<i>Haydarova Namuna</i>	
Using Story-Based Role-Play Activities to Enhance Speaking Skills of Primary School Learners.....	1044
<i>Mohigul Nizomiddinova</i>	
Axborot va telekommunikatsion vositalari imkoniyatlaridan foydalanish orqali talabalarni badiiy qadriyatlarga qiziqtirish.....	1049
<i>Soliyeva Maftuna Tirkash qizi</i>	
Ruhiy rivojlanishning susayish sabablari va klinik xarakteristikasi	1053
<i>Xamrayeva Iroda Sayfullayevna</i>	
Ona tili darslarida zid ma'noli so'zlarning o'quvchilar nutqini rivojlantirishdagi vazifalari	1056
<i>Xusanova Gulruxsor To'liqin qizi</i>	
Ta'lim tizimida neyrolingvistik dasturlash (NLD)ning ilmiy-metodologik asoslari	1059
<i>Xolikova Dilobarxon Maxsitovna</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida milliy identitet va vatanparvarlikni shakllantirish texnologiyalari	1062
<i>Primkulova Iroda Berdimurodovna</i>	
Informatika o'qitishda veb texnologiyalardan foydalanishning ahamiyati	1067
<i>Xatamqulova Gulsanamxon Salimjonovna</i>	
Talabalarning ingliz tilida o'qish ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishda interaktiv metodlardan foydalanish.....	1071
<i>Esmuratov Muzaffar Elamonovich</i>	

MUNDARIJA СОДЕРЖАНИЕ CONTENTS	Bo'lajak maxsus pedagoglarni korreksion mashg'ulotlarda logotexnik mashqlar tizimidan foydalanishga tayyorlash omillari..... 1073 Maxmudov Xurshidjon Shuxratovich Inklyuziv ta'lim jarayonida boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarini antroposentrik yondashuv asosida tarbiyalash mexanizmi 1076 Oppoqxo'jayev Xojixuja Azimjon o'g'li Nutqida muammosi mavjud bolalarning ijtimoiy adaptatsiya xususiyatlarini o'rganishning pedagogik asoslari 1081 Ne'matullayeva Mushtariy Laziz qizi Mutaxassislik modullarini integrativ o'qitishning mazmuni va shart-sharoitlari 1084 Maxmudova Madinaxon Sobirxonovna Talabalarda divergent tafakkurni rivojlantirish usullari 1091 Adizova Nigora Baxtiyorovna Milliy tarbiya tizimida milliy tilning o'rni (jadid pedagoglari qarashlari misolida) 1096 Almuratova Gulbaxor Mansur qizi Kompetensiyaviy ishlab chiqarish bo'yicha pedagogika kollejlari o'quvchilarining o'quv-bilish "yaratish" faol modeli 1100 Ashirov Abdurashid Ravshanovich Bo'lajak ingliz tili o'qituvchilarida deontologik madaniyatning tarkibiy qismlari va pedagogik, psixologik tahlili 1106 Axadova Mahliyo Xalimovna Scientific and Methodological Foundations of the Development of Universal Competencies of Students.. 1109 Bakhtiyor Suvonkulov Maktabgacha 5-6 yoshdagi bolalarni badiiy adabiyot bilan tanishtirishning yosh bilan bog'liq xususiyatlari va tarbiyachining mahorati 1113 Daminova Shoxista Farxodovna Gospital pedagogika – shifoxona va maktab o'rtasidagi ko'prikdir 1117 Dilmurod Alimov Rus tili o'qituvchilarining kasbiy faoliyati asoslari 1121 Ergashov Ma'murjon Mominjonovich Muhandislik ta'limida smart-ta'lim texnologiyalari va adaptiv loyihalash kompetensiyasining nazariy-metodologik asoslari 1125 G. Sh. Tursunova 6–7 yoshli bolalarda ikkinchi tilni o'rgatish orqali ijodiy tafakkurni rivojlantirish: metodik yondashuvlar 1130 G'aniyeva Shahlo Abduqahhor qizi Sun'iy intellekt vositalari orqali bo'lajak o'qituvchilarda axborotlar bilan ishlash kompetensiyasini shakllantirish 1138 Inadullayeva Sevara Qahramonovna Jadid adabiyotini o'qitishda dekonstruktiv yondashuv va samarali pedagogik strategiyalar 1141 Isabayeva Asida Yusufjonovna Kimyo ta'limida natriy va uning birikmalarini o'qitishda pinbord usulining metodik imkoniyatlari..... 1146 Iskandarov Aybek Yuldashevich, Axmedova Nargiza Rustamovna Sifat menejmenti zamonaviy menejmentning funksional xarakteristikasi sifatida..... 1149 Jabbarbergenova Bibimaryam Amangeldiyevna Development of Speed-Strength Abilities of Qualified Wrestlers in Sports Improvement Groups..... 1155 Jumadurdiyev Bahodir Xolmamatovich. Komilov Aziz Xoshimovich Odam va hayvonlar fiziologiyasi fanining oliy ta'lim tizimidagi o'rni va didaktik ahamiyati 1160 Kaljanov Damir Maxsetbayevich Psychological Preparation of Young Judo Players Before and During Competitions 1165 Komilov Aziz Xoshimovich, Jumadurdiyev Bahodir Xolmamatovich Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining kreativ fikrlash qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirish 1171 Komilova Farog'at Numonjon qizi Tarbiya innovativ metodlarining oilada tutgan o'rni..... 1176 Marimbayeva Bibidona Rinat qizi Tibbiyot texnikumi o'quvchilarining mustaqil ishlari orqali kognitiv ko'nikmalarini shakllantirish metodikasi 1180 Matchanova Malika Maxmudovna Pedagogik innovatsiyalar va yangi metodologik yondashuvlar: Design Thinking, Project-Based Learning, Problem-Based Learning onlayn shaklda 1183 Muydinjonov Ziyodjon Rafiqjon o'g'li
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Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlari direktorlarining kasbiy tayyorgarligi va rivojlanishidagi pedagogik shart-sharoitlar	1187
N. Sh. Djumaniyazova	
Badiiy gimnastikachilarda egiluvchanlik sifatini rivojlantirishning nazariy asoslari	1190
Nazarova Mohinur Atxam qizi	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarining metodik tayyorgarligini takomillashtirish texnologiyasi.....	1195
Nishonova Durdona Olimjon qizi	
Politeknikumlarda "Veb dasturlash" fanini o'qitishda sun'iy intellekt texnologiyalaridan foydalanish metodikasi	1201
Nuridinova Gulnigor Taxirjanovna	
O'zbekiston Respublikasi maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlari uchun "Ilk qadam" davlat o'quv dasturi (uchinchi nashri) dagi o'zgarishlar	1205
Otahanova Manzura G'ofurovna	
Sog'lom turmush tarzi vositasida oliy ta'lim muassasasi talabalarining jismoniy salomatligini pedagogik strategiyalar orqali rivojlantirish metodikasi.....	1210
Qayumov Shohruh Abduljalol o'g'li, Norqulov Shokir Muzaffarovich, Karimova Mohinur Abduljalol qizi	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotida yozgi sog'lomlashtirish va chiniqtirish davrida ta'lim-tarbiya jarayoni sifatini ta'minlash	1214
Qurbonova Asal Dilshod qizi	
O'quvchilarining kreativligini rivojlantirish bosqichlari	1218
Safarova Madina Azamat qizi	
Fizika fanini o'qitishda zamonaviy pedagogik texnologiyalardan foydalanish	1222
Shag'ataeva Uldanay O'serbay qizi	
Oliy ta'lim tizimida klasterli yondashuvni qo'llash orqali talabalar induktiv va deduktiv fikrlash ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishning nazariy-metodologik asoslarini takomillashtirish	1227
Shermatova Saxobaxon Rahmonberdi qizi	
Milliy qadriyatlar asosida tasviriy san'atni o'qitishning zamonaviy yondashuvlari	1231
Sherov Dilshod Reyimberganovich	
Ta'lim jarayonida o'qituvchilarni baholashda interaktiv va moslashuvchan usullar	1236
Sayfuddinova Kavsar Rahmatulloh qizi	
Nogiron bolalarni tekshirishda psixologik-pedagogik diagnostikaning ahamiyati	1239
Umarova Sabxon Minavvarovna, Yuldasheva Dilbarxon Turg'unovna	
Ingliz tili darslarida boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining muloqot qobiliyatini rivojlantirish	1242
Xalilova Muxlisa Ulug'bek qizi	
Bo'lajak o'qituvchilarning kreativ qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirish bosqichlari.....	1247
Xayitov Jonibek Xolboboyevich	
Pedagoglarning uzluksiz kasbiy rivojlanish jarayonini individuallashtirishning pedagogik tizimini takomillashtirish	1250
Xudoyberdiyeva Janona Rustamovna	
Bo'lajak pedagoglarning kommunikativ kompetentligini rivojlantirishning psixologik-pedagogik xususiyatlari	1254
Axmedov Akmal Yusufovich, Muhammadjonova Zarnigor Shokirjon qizi	
Boshlang'ich sinflarda matematik mantiqiy fikrlashni rivojlantiruvchi metod va vositalar	1258
Eshonqulova Shafoat Ergashevna, Eshonqulov Sherzod Ummatovich, Samandarova Shahnoza	
Muhandislik ta'limida smart-ta'lim texnologiyalari va adaptiv loyihalash kompetensiyasining nazariy-metodologik asoslari.....	1262
G. Sh. Tursunova	
Professional Needs of Deputy Directors at Secondary Schools.....	1266
Jambilov Nurillo Xabibilloevich	
Virtual reallik texnologiyalari yordamida ta'lim samaradorligini oshirish imkoniyatlari	1269
Mamadjonova Nozima Adhamovna	
AI or Corpus: Which is Better for Teaching English Vocabulary?	1272
Munajat Sultonova	
O'quvchilarni kasbga yo'nal tirishning pedagogik asoslari	1275
Raxmatullayeva Durdona Ravshanovna	
Ingliz tilida talabalarining kasbiy kompetensiyasini rivojlantirish metodikasi (sohaviy matnlarni o'qishni o'rgatish misolida)	1278
Shahobiddinova Dilnavoz Bahodir qizi	

Muhandislik grafikasi ta'limida raqamli transformatsiya: o'quv jarayonini takomillashtirishda zamonaviy pedagogik texnologiyalar (Cad, 3D modellashtirish, VR) roli	1281
<i>Tadjiyeva Feruza Muxtarovna</i>	
Raqamli ta'lim ekotizimi: AKT asosida axborot-ta'lim muhiti va virtual laboratoriyalarni joriy etish tajribasi	1286
<i>Toshkentov Akmal Mamirovich</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarida chiroyli yozish texnologiyalarini rivojlantirish pedagogik muammo sifatida.....	1290
<i>Usmonova Gulnoza Abdurashid qizi</i>	
Теория коммуникации как методологическая основа изучения трансформации языковой нормы в эпоху цифровых медиа.....	1294
<i>Дилшодбеков Темур Дилшодбек угли</i>	
Значение усвоения учебных материалов в процессе формирования биологических понятий у учащихся.....	1297
<i>У. О. Шарибаева</i>	
Specifics of Teaching Professional Terminology to Students of Economic Specialties	1301
<i>Хамдамов Рамзбек Мадаминжонович</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarida tarbiyalanuvchilarni kasbga yo'naltirish: pedagogik yondashuvlar va amaliy tajribalar.....	1306
<i>Ahmedova Lola Abdivasi qizi</i>	
Madaniyat tushunchasi va uni xorijiy til o'qitishda o'rganish zarurati.....	1311
<i>Ma'murova Farangiz Ne'matovna</i>	
Grafik organayzer tushunchasining mohiyati va uning turlari	1315
<i>Nabijanov Yusufjon Inomiddin o'g'li</i>	
Bo'lajak boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarining kasbiy kompetensiyasini shakllantirish va rivojlantirishning ilmiy metodik asoslari.....	1319
<i>Xidirova Gavhar Babaqul qizi</i>	
Pedagogik nizo va stress holatlarida o'qituvchining o'zini boshqarish malakasini shakllantirish	1322
<i>Razzakova Dilnoza Akramovna</i>	
Kompyuter grafikasi darslarida loyihaviy yondashuvni amalga oshirishning metodik asoslari.....	1326
<i>Nazarova Shahnoza Shokirovna</i>	
Kichik yoshdagi o'quvchilarda universal ta'limiy faoliyatlarni shakllantirish nazariyasi.....	1330
<i>Abdullayev A'zimjon Abduvali o'g'li</i>	
ART pedagogikaning tarixi va kelib chiqishi	1335
<i>M. K. Abulova</i>	
Dasturiy-didaktik ta'minot asosida talabalarning kiberpedagogik kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirish metodikasini takomillashtirish	1338
<i>Bekchonova Shoira Bazarbayevna</i>	
Bo'lajak pedagoglarning fasilitatsion kompetentligini raqamli texnologiyalar vositasida rivojlantirish mexanizmi	1342
<i>Eshmatova Go'zaloy Ziyoyidin qizi</i>	
Mashqalali o'qitiladigan qaraqalpaq adabiyati sabafiganda qollanilgan abzalliqdari	1346
<i>Jaksimova Urziya Jumabaevna</i>	
Forming Primary-School Teachers' Creative Pedagogical Culture Through Professional Reflection.....	1349
<i>Komiljonova Dilyoraxon</i>	
Professional ta'limda o'quvchilarda tadqiqotchilik ko'nikmalarini shakllantirishning nazariy-metodik asoslari (fizika ta'limi misolida).....	1352
<i>Kosimova Yanglish Baxtiyorovna</i>	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarga ta'lim-tarbiya berishda ertak terapiyasidan foydalanish	1355
<i>Mamataliyeva Mahbuba Abduvoris qizi</i>	
Oliy ta'lim muassasalarida imkoniyati cheklangan talabalarni ijtimoiy moslashtirish tizimini takomillashtirishning nazariy-pedagogik asoslari	1358
<i>Nazarova Zarrina Allaberdiyevna</i>	
Mantiqiy fikrlashni rivojlantirish texnologiyalari asosida pedagogik loyihalashtirish	1361
<i>Polvonova Yulduzxon Saparboyevna</i>	
SMART texnologiyalar asosida bo'lajak boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilari kasbiy mahoratini shakllantirish modeli	1364
<i>Qipchaqova Yorqinoy Hamidjonovna</i>	
Talabalarda emotsional intellektni boshqarishning ijtimoiy-psixologik usullari.....	1368
<i>Rustamova Barno Abduxalilovna</i>	

Nofilologik ta'lim yo'nalishi talabalariga chet tili o'qitish jarayonida pragmatik kompetensiyani rivojlantirish xususiyatlari.....	1371
Sadirova Dinara Sadikovna	
The Effectiveness of Project-Based Collaborative Learning in Improving English Speaking Skills of High School Students.....	1378
Salikhova N. I., Izzetullah Zeki	
Jadidlarning pedagogik merosi va zamonaviy ta'limda akmeologik yondashuv integratsiyasi.....	1383
Shodiyeva Nasiba Rustamovna	
Serebral falajli bolalar uchun xavfsiz muhit yaratish.....	1387
Shokirova Shaxnoza Dilmurodovna	
Diplomatik hujjatlar bilan ishlashning pedagogik modeli	1391
Sobirova Shahlo Jamolovna	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarini kreativ fikrlashga o'rgatishning zamonaviy usullari.....	1394
Suyarov Adham Begmuradovich	
Globalization and The Changing Role of English Teachers in Non-Native Contexts	1399
Toirova Shohida Kamolovna	
The Role of the Literary Heritage of the Timurid Era in Shaping National Identity and Spiritual Values	1402
Tokhliyeva Shafolat Rustam kizi	
Mantiqiy fikrlashni rivojlantirishning mavjud ilmiy-nazariy tavsiflari	1405
Toshboyeva Saida	
Talabalarning mustaqil ish loyihagini ishlash jarayonidagi ruhiy holatlari	1408
Uzaqbaeva Venera Abatbaevna, Kubeysinova Nilufar Maxmutovna	
O'qituvchilarda mantiqiy fikrlash kompetensiyasini shakllantirishning mazmuni va mexanizmlari	1412
Xursanova Zilola Mirzaxolmatovna	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarda ijtimoiy-emotsional kompetensiyalarni shakllantirish: metod va yondashuvlar	1416
Ziyayev Adxamjon	
Developing Students' Speech Skills Based on Multimodal Approach in English Teaching	1419
Bultakova Mokhinur Shuhratboy qizi	
Kreativ yondashuv asosida talabalarni tarbiyaviy faoliyatga tayyorlashning samarali yo'llari	1422
G. M. Adizova	
A Comparative Study of Linguistic and Cultural Expression in Uzbek and English Literary Discourse.....	1426
Ismoilova Shakhnoza Ilkhomovna	
Fitrat asarlarida vatanparvarlik va milliy ong masalalarining talqini.....	1429
Isomiddinov Yo'ldosh Yusubboyevich	
Bo'lajak tarbiyachilarni pedagogik mahoratni egallash jarayonini takomillashtirish.....	1433
Jabborova Marifat Qodiraliyevna	
Umumta'lim maktablarida ijtimoiy sheriklik asosida ta'lim samaradorligini oshirish mexanizmlari	1436
Kumush Xamrakulova	
Ekologik bilimlar asosida maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda tabiatga qadriyatli munosabatlarni shakllantirishning tarixiy asoslarini o'rganishda xorijiy tajribalar.....	1440
Mirxamidova Maftunaxon Xusanboy qizi	
O'yin nomlarining lingvomadaniy ahamiyati	1444
Matmusayeva Muhayyo Azamovna	
Umumta'lim maktablarida elektroliz jarayonini o'qitish metodikasi	1446
O'rinova Ozodaxon O'ljayevna, Toshtemirov Asadbek	
Bo'lajak maktabgacha ta'lim tizimi pedagoglarining ekoestetik madaniyatini rivojlantirishda ekologik ta'lim-tarbiyaning o'рни	1450
Oygul Ashurova Anvarjonovna	
Inklyuziv ta'limda alohida ta'lim ehtiyojlari bo'lgan bolalar majburiyat yuklatilgan shaxslar emas.....	1453
Mo'minov Sulton Akbar o'g'li, Toshmurodova Muxabbat Nazaraliyevna	
Nogironligi bo'lgan o'smir bolalarni ota-onalari bilan hamkorlikda ijtimoiy hayotga moslashtirish samaradorligini oshirish.....	1460
Salixova Gulnoza Maxmudovna	
Talabalarning o'quv faoliyatini o'yinli texnologiyalar asosida tashkil etishning nazariy asoslari	1463
Umarov Nurbek Irkinovich	
Maxsus maktablarda eshitishida nuqsoni bor bolalar nutqini interfaol metodlar orqali rivojlantirish	1466
Teshaboyeva Feruza Raximovna	

THE ROLE OF THE LITERARY HERITAGE OF THE TIMURID ERA IN SHAPING NATIONAL IDENTITY AND SPIRITUAL VALUES

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Abstract: This article examines the role of the rich literary heritage of the Timurid era in shaping national identity and spiritual values. Special attention is devoted to the works of eminent figures such as Alisher Navoiy, Abdurahmon Jomiy, and Zahiriddin Muhammad Bobur, who emphasized ideas of human perfection, justice, compassion, moral purity, and national self-awareness. The article also explores how the literary heritage of the Timurid period contributes to enriching the spirituality of modern society.

Key words: Timurid era, literary heritage, national idea, spirituality, Navoiy, Bobur, values.

Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada Temuriylar davrida shakllangan boy adabiy merosning milliy g'oya va ma'naviy qadriyatlarini shakllantirishdagi o'rni hamda ahamiyati tahlil qilinadi. Ayniqsa, Alisher Navoiy, Abdurahmon Jomiy va Zahiriddin Muhammad Bobur kabi ijodkorlarning asarlarida komillik, adolat, mehr-oqibat, axloqiy poklik va milliy o'zlikni anglash g'oyalari yoritilganligi ta'kidlanadi. Maqolada, shuningdek, Temuriylar davri adabiyotining hozirgi davr ma'naviyatini boyitishdagi dolzarb jihatlari ham ko'rib chiqiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Temuriylar davri, adabiy meros, milliy g'oya, ma'naviyat, Navoiy, Bobur, qadriyatlar.

Аннотация: В статье анализируется роль богатого литературного наследия эпохи Тимуридов в формировании национальной идеи и духовных ценностей. Особое внимание уделено произведениям таких выдающихся творцов, как Алишер Навои, Абдурахман Джамии и Захириддин Мухаммад Бабур, в которых отражены идеи совершенства, справедливости, милосердия, нравственной чистоты и национального самосознания. Также рассматриваются актуальные аспекты влияния литературы эпохи Тимуридов на обогащение духовности современного общества.

Ключевые слова: эпоха Тимуридов, литературное наследие, национальная идея, духовность, Навои, Бабур, ценности.

INTRODUCTION

The Timurid era, spanning the 14th–15th centuries, marks a period of extraordinary cultural and literary flourishing in Central Asia. Under the rule of Amir Temur and his descendants, literature became not only a means of artistic expression but also a powerful tool for shaping moral and national consciousness. The works created during this time embodied humanistic ideals, spiritual refinement, and the affirmation of national identity, which continue to play an important role in the cultural development of modern Uzbekistan. The literary achievements of this period are closely connected to the rise of the Chagatai literary language, which later evolved into modern Uzbek. Poets and thinkers of the Timurid court were not only artists but also ideologists who contributed to forming the cultural memory and moral foundations of the nation. The literary heritage of the Timurid era represents one of the brightest periods in the history of Central Asian civilization. This era not only enriched world culture with outstanding poetic and philosophical works but also laid the foundation for the formation of national identity, spiritual values, and moral principles. In the modern world, where processes of globalization often lead to cultural homogenization, returning to and rethinking historical cultural heritage is an important factor in preserving and strengthening national self-awareness.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The ideas expressed by Alisher Navoiy, Abdurahmon Jomiy, and Zahiriddin Muhammad Bobur remain relevant today because they address universal human values such as justice, enlightenment, spiritual maturity, compassion, and patriotism. These principles not only helped shape the national idea during the Timurid era

but also continue to serve as a moral and cultural compass for contemporary society. Studying this heritage allows us to understand how literature can contribute to nation-building, moral education, and cultural continuity. Therefore, this research is highly relevant in the context of preserving spiritual values, strengthening national identity, and promoting intercultural understanding in the 21st century.

The study of the literary heritage of the Timurid era began in the 19th century, when European orientalis and Russian scholars first turned their attention to the cultural and intellectual achievements of Central Asia. Among the earliest researchers were Vasily Bartold and Vladimir Minorsky, whose works laid the foundation for systematic academic inquiry into Timurid literature, language, and history. Their research emphasized the global significance of the Timurid cultural renaissance and its contribution to world civilization. In the 20th century, the study of Timurid literary heritage gained further momentum through the works of Central Asian and Uzbek scholars. Researchers such as Abdurauf Fitrat, Ibrohim Mo'minov, and Ozod Sharafiddinov made significant contributions to analyzing the literary, linguistic, and ideological dimensions of this period, highlighting the role of Timurid literature in shaping the cultural and spiritual identity of the Uzbek nation. In the 21st century, interest in Timurid studies has grown even further due to the increasing recognition of cultural heritage as a key component of national identity. Contemporary Uzbek scholars such as Naim Karimov, Ibrohim G'afurov, and Abduqodir Hayitmetov, along with numerous young researchers, are conducting in-depth studies of Alisher Navoiy, Zahiriddin Muhammad Bobur, and their contemporaries. Their research focuses on literary analysis, linguistic features, philosophical ideas, and the role of these works in nation-building and cultural transmission.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Today, Timurid literary heritage is studied not only within Uzbekistan but also in research centers across Europe, the United States, Turkey, and other countries. The field continues to expand through interdisciplinary approaches that combine literary studies, cultural history, linguistics, and digital humanities. The reign of Amir Temur established strong political and cultural foundations for the promotion of arts and sciences. His successors, especially Husayn Boyqaro, continued this policy by turning Herat into one of the world's leading cultural centers of the 15th century. Madrasahs, libraries, and literary salons encouraged intellectual exchange, laying the groundwork for the development of humanist thought in literature.

Figure 1: Role of Timurid literary heritage in shaping national identity and spirituality

Literary activity during the Timurid period reflected the synthesis of Turkic and Persian cultural traditions. This multicultural environment enriched poetic imagery, language, and themes, making the literature of this era both universal and deeply national in character.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

A key feature of Timurid literature was its moral and spiritual orientation. Poets such as Alisher Navoiy expressed in their works the ideals of justice, truth, and human dignity. In his masterpiece *Khamsa*, Navoiy conveys the idea of the perfect human being (*inson-e komil*), whose moral and intellectual maturity ensures the prosperity of society. His poetry also promoted the values of unity, compassion, and respect for cultural diversity. Similarly, Abdurahmon Jomiy's philosophical and mystical works emphasized spiritual enlightenment, divine love, and moral discipline. Zahiriddin Muhammad Bobur, in his poetic and prose works—particularly in *Boburnoma*—combined personal experience with historical reflection, thereby strengthening national self-awareness and respect for heritage.

These literary figures created not only artistic masterpieces but also ethical guidelines that contributed to the moral education of society.

The national idea of any people is rooted in historical memory, language, and shared values. Timurid literature played a crucial role in forming and transmitting these values through poetic narratives and philosophical reflections. The ideal of a just ruler, reverence for knowledge, and the elevation of the human spirit became central themes that influenced later generations. Furthermore, the Timurid literary heritage helped shape linguistic identity, as Chagatai Turkic emerged as a prestigious literary language. This not only strengthened the sense of national belonging but also enabled the transmission of cultural values to a broad audience. Today, the spiritual and moral messages embedded in Timurid literature remain highly relevant. In a globalizing world, where cultural identities face new challenges, the ideas of Navoiy, Jomiy, and Bobur serve as a moral compass and a source of cultural pride. Their emphasis on education, tolerance, justice, and unity continues to resonate with modern national development strategies and educational programs in Uzbekistan.

Table 1: Role of the Timurid literary heritage in shaping national idea and spirituality

No	Literary figure / source	Core ideas and spiritual values	Influence on national idea	Modern relevance
1	Alisher Navoiy	Human perfection, justice, enlightenment, compassion	Strengthening national identity through education and moral values	Serves as a spiritual foundation for raising an educated and ethical generation
2	Abdurahmon Jomiy	Spiritual purity, Sufism, moral awakening	Deepening ethical values and faith	Highlights the importance of spiritual heritage in moral education
3	Zahiriddin Muhammad Bobur	Patriotism, historical memory, honesty and justice	Strengthens national pride and historical consciousness	Encourages youth to develop patriotism and loyalty to the homeland
4	Timurid literary environment	Justice, promotion of knowledge, arts and culture	Formed the idea of national unity and progress	Provides historical experience for modern cultural and educational policy

Incorporating the literary heritage of the Timurid era into modern cultural and educational policy contributes to strengthening national identity and fostering intercultural understanding.

CONCLUSION

The literary heritage of the Timurid era is not only a historical treasure but also a living source of national ideas and spiritual development. Through their profound moral and philosophical messages, Timurid writers shaped the foundations of a cultural identity that continue to inspire contemporary society. By studying and promoting this heritage, it becomes possible to build stronger connections between the past and the future, ensuring the continuity of national and spiritual values.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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